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Application of Castables Manufactured by RMS, a.s. Košice in Pusher Furnaces

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ABSTRACT

In 2010, a monolithic hearth made of low-cement KOFOND LC 18 castable was first used in pusher furnace No. 3 at U. S. Steel Košice, s.r.o. This operational hearth lining contributed to the production of a record number of extruded slabs. Since then, the market share of unshaped materials has grown at the expense of other building materials. This is due to the energy intensity of refractory materials production and the introduction of new monolithic lining installation technologies. This article describes the practical application of castables manufactured for use in the pusher furnaces at RMS, a.s. Košice. RMS, a.s. Košice has installed a wide assortment of insulation and metallurgical castables using various material bases with different cement content (MCC, LCC, ULCC and NCC) in its production program.

1. Introduction

One of the key trends in the steel-making industry is the use of high quality refractories, resistant to the external corrosive environment. Increased quality requirements for refractory materials are being introduced, but it must be done with minimal economic impact. This means increasing the life cycle of heat aggregate while reducing refractory-spe-

cific consumption, improving productivity and saving energy. Application of monolithic linings is one of the available options. In 2010, the operational lining of the pusher furnace (PF) hearth was changed at

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Fig. 1 • New corundum blocks

Fig. 2 • Worn corundum blocks

U. S. Steel Košice, s.r.o. The original molten corundum blocks were replaced with a lining made of high-alumina castable. The first monolithic hearth lining of the pusher furnace installed in 2010 was made of low-cement KOFOND LC 18 castable. The extended life cycle of this monolithic hearth has witnessed production of a record number of extruded slabs.

2. PF hearth lining

Pusher furnaces are an important element of metallurgical production processing at U. S. Steel Košice, s.r.o. The performance and quality of slab heating considerably affects the quality of a rolled material. The lining of the hearth is one of the main factors affecting the operation and final product quality of a continuous pusher furnace.

The permanent lining of the hearth consists of several layers of insulation and refractory material. Rigorous requirements are imposed on the operational lining of the hearth in difficult high-temperature conditions:

- Avoid impacting the temperature zone and the surface quality of a heated object
- Withstand high temperatures and sudden temperature changes
- Undergo minimum linear and volume changes
- Resist the chemical effects of scaling and furnace atmosphere
- Resist abrasion and mechanical impact; and
- Achieve sufficient life cycle with minimum maintenance.

The original operational linings of the hearth were made of molten corundum blocks (Fig. 1) showing high strength and abrasion resistance and low porosity (2–8 %). The disadvantage of corundum blocks is their high thermal conductivity (5–7 W/m·K at 1300 °C), resulting in significant escape of heat from the furnace hearth to the environment (heat losses) and poor temperature regulation in the slab profile. Due to relatively high dilatation, the molten blocks were placed on dry spreading. The dilatation resulted in lower stability and relocation of individual rows of blocks, especially along the furnace length. Frequent temperature changes in the pusher furnace caused gradual wear to the operational layer of the lining (Fig. 2), degradation of temperature zone homogeneity and increased accumulation of surface scales.

Wearing of blocks and scale build-ups resulted in frequent repairs of the hearth and added to pusher furnace downtime. Mechanical procedures and/or powerful water streams were used to repair the hearth. Temperature changes in the furnaces induced tensions in the corundum blocks due to thermal expansion. The tension damages the structure of the hearth lining surface (Fig. 3). Deteriorated corundum block surfac-

Fig. 3 • Corundum block hearth after removal of scales

Fig. 4 • Flat surface of monolithic hearth

es caused mechanical damage (grooves) in the bottom sections of steel slabs, resulting in sub-standard production output.

In May 2010, LCC castable KOFOND LC 18 was applied in a new technical design of the pusher furnace 3 hearth lining. See Table 1 for the physical and chemical properties of KOFOND LC 18 castable.

Table 1 · KOFOND LC 18 technical parameters

BD _{110 °C} / kg·m ⁻³	BD _{1650 °C} / kg·m ⁻³	CCS _{110 °C} / MPa	CCS _{1650 °C} / MPa	CMOR _{110 °C} / MPa	CMOR _{1650 °C} / MPa	PLC _{1650 °C} / %	Water demand / mass-%	Al ₂ O ₃ content / mass-%	CaO content / mass-%
typ. 3110	typ. 3070	min. 70	min. 90	typ. 7	typ. 25	-0.1	4.5-5	min. 94	typ. 1.8

Fig. 5 · KOFOND LC 18 thermal conductivity

Fig. 6 · KOFOND LC 18 thermal expansion

United States Steel Corporation has developed standards for evaluation of refractories intended for PF hearths. To assess the fitness of KOFOND LC 18 castable, U. S. Steel Europe Research and Development carried out a series of tests, including instantaneous temperature change resistance, thermal expansion, thermo-gravimetry, differential thermal analysis and corrosion tests with various grades of steel. KOFOND LC 18 is based on corundum and additives with hydraulic bonding and is intended for processing by casting and vibrating. The maximum usage temperature is 1750 °C. The material has high resistance against sudden temperature changes, high thermal and mechanical properties and good resistance against molten metal and slag. The castable also has excellent resistance against scale build-up. It provides a flat hearth surface (Fig. 4) with resulting improvement of heated slab quality. Due to the lower thermal conductivity of the castable (Fig. 5) compared to corundum blocks, thermal losses through the furnace casing are reduced to 3 W/m·K at 1200 °C. Smaller thermal differences between top and bottom surfaces improves the thermal homogeneity profile of heated slabs.

Application of unshaped refractory materials is advantageous since monolithic hearth lining with minimum joints involves fast and simple installation. Lower physical load during application and repairs results in reduced risk of injuries. Less workload results in savings of refractory material and decreased refractory labour cost.

The thermal expansion of the castable (1.046 % at 1200 °C, Fig. 6) depends on expansion of its individual phases. It characterises the reversible dimensional change of the material. It is important information for design of the size, number and thicknesses of the individual panels used in construction of monolithic hearth linings for pusher furnaces. For successful start-up to operational temperatures, correct dimensioning of construction joints in the lining is critical. Drying processes and start-up to operating temperature are controlled by a system of thermocouples installed directly in, and on the surface of the castable. The input power of ceiling heaters in the individual PF zones is regulated by the control system.

3. Overhaul of PF 3 hearth

At U. S. Steel Košice, s.r.o., the operational lining of the hearth was constructed by in-situ application of castables using panel casting. The total area of hearth minus the part containing off-take grooves was approximately 120 m².

A layer of hard refractory KOSAM TB building material 65 mm thick was placed directly into the panels as levelled permanent lining (Fig. 8). Ready castable of 190 mm thickness was then installed in a checkerboard pattern in the individual panels (Fig. 9). After the castable was cured, the casing was removed and construction joints were filled with rockwool. Thermocouples to control drying and operational temperature start-up were placed directly in the bottom layer of castable above the permanent lining as well as on the surface of the castable.

In July 2015, a scheduled repair of pusher furnace 3 was completed. Monolithic hearth lining made of KOFOND LC 18 castable had by then reached a record life cycle – 5.239 mil. extruded slabs. An overhaul of the hearth was carried out after inspection of the PF. No major damage was found in the main section of the hearth. The castable thickness in the centre was 120 mm compared to the original 185 mm (Fig. 10). Only minimal penetration of scales into the castable was observed in hearth lining cross-sections. The maximum surface layer build-up was 10–20 mm (Fig. 11). Scale accumulation increased at the PF exit (off-take grooves) where scaling reached 60 mm. An integrated flat layer of scales not requiring any cleaning and special maintenance is very desirable. More significant wear of the operational lining was visible at the margins of the furnace. The side edges of the slabs created a track 600 mm wide due to mechanical action (Fig. 12). In this area, the lowest residual thicknesses, approx. 40 mm, were observed (Fig. 13).

Based on experience since 2010 with the new PF 3 hearth refractory lining solution, the same method was used for the remaining pusher furnaces (Table 2). Use of KOFOND LC 18 castable on the bottom of the pusher furnaces resulted in reduction of damage (scratching) to the bottom

Fig.7 • Project for monolithic lining repair - RMS, a.s. Košice

Fig.8 • Brick under-layer in the panel formwork

Fig.9 • Panel casting completion

surface of slabs and improved homogenisation of the thermal profile of heated slabs.

A refractory lining of the exit doors of the pusher furnace was installed at U. S. Steel Košice, s.r.o. using KOPORO 011, KOPORO 012 and KOPORO 0165 grade thermal-insulation castables. It was necessary to harmonise the strength characteristics of insulation castable with operational conditions to guarantee an extended life cycle. The highest level of thermal shocks, vibrations and impacts is present at the exit doors.

For thermal protection of skids and skid stands in the pusher furnaces used at U. S. Steel Košice, s.r.o. (Fig. 14) and in other companies, mono-

lithic precast units of various types made of high-alumina KOFOND F6A-1 castable are used.

4. Other unshaped materials used in pusher furnaces

In addition to castable for PF hearths, RMS, a.s. Košice is a supplier of other types of castable that help ensure continuous operation of pusher furnaces.

Gunning castables of grade KOTOR T07A-1 or KOTOR T07A-3 (Table 3)

Fig. 10 • Residual thickness of castable in the centre of the hearth

Fig. 13 • Residual thickness of castable after mechanical wear

Fig. 11 • Scale build-up thickness

Fig. 14 • Covers of pusher furnace stands and skids

Fig. 12 • Mechanical wear at the hearth edge

based on andalusite with additives are used for hot and cold repair of pusher furnaces. They are also applied to off-take grooves by hot spraying and are used for local repairs of flue chimneys during pusher furnace outages.

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Monolithic blocks made of castable KOFOND FA 5 are designed for the supporting structure of the leading edge permanent lining under the monolithic hearth.

Insulation castables were also used for local repairs of the PF ceiling. Cement-free KOFOND A 60 NP castable (Table 4) with andalusite base and additives was successfully used for worn furnace ceilings (Figs. 15 and 16).

Heating of objects in the pusher furnace is provided by a combination of ceiling radiation and bottom vortex front burners. To save energy, a project to more effectively utilise heating gas (a mix of BF gas, coking gas and natural gas) was completed in the pusher furnaces. The design included

Table 2 • Volume of heated slabs processed in pusher furnaces as of July 1, 2017

Pusher furnace	Volume of cast slabs (thousand tons)	Date of castable application
PF 1	0,923	August 2016
PF 2	1,406	February 2016
PF 3	1,973	August 2015
PF 4	3,964	July 2013

Fig. 15 und 16 • Local repair of pusher furnace ceiling with KOFOND A 60 NP castable

Table 3 • KOTOR T07A-1 and KOTOR T07A-3 technical parameters

Material	BD _{110°C} / kg·m ⁻³	BD _{1550°C} / kg·m ⁻³	CCS _{110°C} / MPa	CCS _{1550°C} / MPa	Grain size / mm	PLC _{1550°C} / %	Al ₂ O ₃ content / mass-%	CaO content / mass-%	Fe ₂ O ₃ content / mass-%
KOTOR T07A-1	typ. 2420	typ. 2270	min. 30	min. 40	0–4	typ. – 0.4	min. 60	typ. 5	max. 1.1
KOTOR T07A-3	typ. 2360	typ. 2320	typ. 30	typ. 40	0–4	typ. – 0.7	min. 60	typ. 5	max. 1.1

Table 4 • KOFOND A 60 NP technical parameters

Test temperature	BD / kg·m ⁻³	CCS / MPa	PLC / %	Grain size / mm	Water demand / mass-%	Al ₂ O ₃ content / mass-%	CaO content / mass-%	Fe ₂ O ₃ content / mass-%
110 °C/24 h	typ. 2470	typ. 30	-	0–6	6–6.5	typ. 60	typ. 0.2	typ. 1
1200 °C/5 h	typ. 2450	typ. 90	typ. 0					
1600 °C/5 h	typ. 2360	typ. 100	typ. 1					

an inclined wall (slanted) in the bottom pre-heating zone directing the exit flue gas as close as possible to the bottom slab edge to provide secondary heating of furnace objects. The project, delivery of refractory materials (KOSAM TB, KOFOND F4S, KOLAS 130 and KOLAS 50) and refractory installation were carried out in cooperation with the U. S. Steel Košice, s.r.o. Development department.

5. Conclusions

A new technical approach employing monolithic hearth lining in the pusher furnaces at U. S. Steel Košice, s.r.o. has proved to be an effective solution. Application of this method resulted in material, energy and la-

bour savings. Experience with monolithic linings made of high quality castable in pusher furnaces indicates that the linings can be successfully applied and result in operational and economic benefits.